

STUDY OF SEVERE IRON DEFICIENCY ANAEMIA DURING LABOUR

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ABSTRACT

Anemia among pregnant women is a serious global health concern, iron deficiency anemia being the most common cause of anemia. Iron deficiency is common during pregnancy due to increased iron requirement which is not easily fulfilled by dietary intake especially when iron bio availability is poor. Severe iron deficiency anemia during labour has adverse labour outcomes, postpartum haemorrhage being the most common and serious adverse outcome.

KEYWORDS: Iron deficiency anemia, post partum haemorrhage, labour complications.

INTRODUCTION

Iron deficiency anaemia (IDA) remains a public health challenge, especially among pregnant women in developing countries. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), over 32 million pregnant women globally are anaemic, with 0.8 million classified as severely anaemic.^[1] In India, where dietary iron intake is often insufficient and bioavailability is low, IDA accounts for over 90% of anaemia cases during pregnancy.^[2]

The WHO defines anaemia in pregnancy as haemoglobin levels <11 g/dL, with severe anaemia defined as <7 g/dL.^[3] Prevalence rates of anaemia in pregnancy in India have been reported as high as 70–80%.^[4] particularly in rural and socioeconomically disadvantaged populations. This has grave implications during labour, where increased physiological stress can amplify the risks posed by depleted iron stores.

Severe IDA in labour is linked with several adverse outcomes including preterm birth, low birth weight (LBW), postpartum haemorrhage (PPH), maternal cardiac failure, and increased perinatal mortality.^[5,6] Furthermore, anaemia reduces a woman's tolerance to blood loss during delivery, potentially leading to rapid decompensation and maternal death.^[7]

Despite a high burden, limited literature exists on the

real-world impact of severe IDA on labour outcomes in Indian tertiary care settings. This prospective observational study was conducted to evaluate maternal and fetal outcomes in women with severe iron deficiency anaemia during labour, and to identify contributing sociodemographic and clinical factors.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design and Setting

This was a prospective observational study conducted in Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology at a Tertiary Hospital for a period of two years.

Sample Size and Selection Criteria

A total of 100 antenatal women admitted in labour with severe iron deficiency anaemia were selected randomly after obtaining informed consent. Severe anaemia is defined as haemoglobin <7 g/dL based based on WHO guidelines.^[3]

Inclusion Criteria

- Pregnant women admitted during labour
- Gestational age >20 weeks in labour
- Haemoglobin <7 g/dL at the time of admission during labour
- Willingness to provide informed consent

Exclusion Criteria

- Anaemia due to acute or chronic haemorrhage

- Multiple pregnancies
- Women with comorbid conditions such as thromboembolism, renal, hepatic, or cardiac disorders
- Known cases of haemolytic anaemia or bleeding disorders
- Recent blood transfusion within the last 15 days
- Cases of DIC or HELLP syndrome

Data Collection

Detailed history including sociodemographic profile, dietary habits, obstetric history, antenatal care (ANC) visits, and presenting symptoms were recorded. A thorough clinical examination and obstetric assessment were performed.

Investigations included.

- Complete hemogram
- Red blood cell indices (MCV, MCH, MCHC)
- Peripheral smear
- Serum ferritin
- Serum iron
- vitamin B12

OUTCOME MEASURES

Maternal outcomes Studied

- Type of labour (spontaneous/induced)
- Mode of delivery
- Occurrence of complications such as PPH, preterm labour, hypertensive disorders, sepsis, wound complications, and maternal mortality

Neonatal outcomes studied.

- Birth weight
- APGAR score
- NICU admission
- Stillbirths and neonatal deaths

Treatment Details

Interventions such as oral or parenteral iron therapy (iron sucrose or ferric carboxymaltose), blood transfusion, and intervention during labour were documented. Data on management choices were analysed in relation to outcomes.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were tabulated and analysed using Microsoft Excel and SPSS software (version 20). Descriptive statistics were used for demographic variables. Pearson's correlation was employed to assess relationships between education, ANC visits, parity, and haemoglobin levels. A p-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

RESULTS

1. Demographic Profile

Age Distribution: In this study the average age of the study population was 25.23 years (range 18– 36 years). The largest group was aged 20–24 years (43%), followed by 25–29 years (35%), >30 years (19%), and <20 years

(3%).

Age group (in years)	Number of Cases (%)
<20	3%
20-24	43%
25-29	35%
>30	19%

Socioeconomic Status: In this study 65% patients belonged to lower socio-economic class and 35% belonged to middle socioeconomic status according to modified Kuppuswamy scale.

Socioeconomic status	Number of Cases (%)
Lower	65%
Middle	35%

Booking Status: Out of all the cases studied 38% patients were booked and 62% were unbooked.

Booking status	Number of Cases (%)
Booked	38%
Unbooked	62%

Residence: In this study 60% patients were from rural areas and 40% patients were from urban area.

Residence	Number of Cases (%)
Rural	60%
Urban	40%

Dietary Habits: 56% cases were vegetarian and 44% consumed mixed diet.

Vegetarian	56%
Mixed diet	44%

2. Obstetric History

Gravidity: In the studied cases, 87% were multigravida and only 13% were primigravida.

Gravida	Number of Cases (%)
Primigravida	13%
Multigravida	87%

Gestational Age at Admission: Out of the patients admitted, mean gestational age at admission was 36.35 weeks, out of which 17% cases were extreme preterm (<34 weeks), 28% were preterm (34-37 weeks and 63% cases were > 37 weeks.

Gestational age	Number of Cases (%)
<34 weeks	17%
34-37 weeks	28%
>37 weeks	63%

Clinical Presentation: Most common presenting complaints for these patients was generalised weakness accounting 38% cases, giddiness in 24% cases, pedal

Seema in 18% cases and breathlessness in 16% cases.

Symptoms	Number of Cases (%)
Generalised weakness	38%
Giddiness	24%
Pedal oedema	18%
Breathlessness	16%

3. Laboratory Findings

Peripheral Smear: Microcytic hypochromic anaemia was found in 74% cases and Normocytic normochromic

anemia was found in 26% cases.

Peripheral smear	Number of Cases (%)
Microcytic hypochromic	74%
Normocytic normochromic	26%

4. Maternal Complications

Most common complication observed was preterm labour in 45% cases. A single maternal death occurred in a patient with severe anaemia, pre-eclampsia, and sepsis.

Complication	Frequency (%)
Preterm labour	45%
Gestational hypertension	10%
Postpartum haemorrhage	9%
Wound complications (Wound gap)	4% LSCS wound gap 4% episiotomy wound gap
Abruptio placenta	6%
Sepsis	6%
Intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR)	5%
Placenta previa	2%
Congestive heart failure	2%
Maternal mortality	1%

5. Neonatal Outcome

Out of all the deliveries, 63% babies born were low birth weight less than 2.5 kg.

Outcome	Number of Cases (%)
Low birth weight (<2500g)	63%
- Very low birth weight (1000-1500g)	11%
- Extremely low birth weight (<1000g)	2%
NICU admissions	27%
Stillbirths	13%
Neonatal deaths	2%

6. Treatment Given

59% cases presenting with severe anemia during labour were treated with blood and blood components. For those not accepting blood transfusion, injectable or oral iron was given.

Treatment Modality	No. of Patients (%)
Blood and blood components	59%
Injectable iron only (iron sucrose or FCM)	34%
Oral iron only	7%
Blood + Injectable iron	3%

7. Mode of Delivery

In this study, 47% cases went into spontaneous labour, 29% cases were induced for labour, emergency c-section was performed in 24% cases and 2% cases had instrumental vaginal delivery.

Mode of Delivery	Number of Cases (%)
Spontaneous vaginal delivery	47%
Induced vaginal delivery	29%
Cesarean section (Emergency)	24%
Instrumental delivery	2%

Average Haemoglobin at delivery: average haemoglobin values in Vaginal delivery group was found to be 6.04 ± 0.70 g/dL and in Caesarian section group was 6.12 ± 0.75 g/dL.

Mode of delivery	Number of Cases (%)	Average haemoglobin (g/dl)
Vaginal delivery	74%	6.04± 0.70
Cesarean section	26%	6.12 ±0.75

8. Outcomes

Primary Outcome	Spontaneous labour (n=63)	Induced / Augmented labour (n=37)	Total (n=100)
Post partum haemorrhage	6(9.5%)	3 (8.1%)	9
Mortality	1	0	0
Secondary Outcome			
LSCS	16(25.3%)	8(21.6%)	24
ICU admission	3	0	0

Primary outcome: Out of the 63 cases of spontaneous labour, 6 cases (9.5%) had postpartum haemorrhage and 3 cases (8.1%) out of 37 cases who were induced or augmented for labour had postpartum haemorrhage.

Secondary outcome: Out of total cases studied, 24 cases were taken up for emergency LSCS and 3 cases were admitted in ICU for postpartum management.

9. Correlation Findings

- Education vs Interpregnancy interval: Significant correlation ($p = 0.013$)
- Gravidity vs ANC visits: Negative correlation – as gravidity increased, ANC visits decreased ($p < 0.001$)
- Parity vs Haemoglobin levels: Negative correlation – increasing parity associated with lower Hb ($p = 0.003$)

DISCUSSION

Iron deficiency anaemia (IDA) continues to be a major public health concern, particularly in developing countries like India where nutritional deficiencies, socioeconomic disparities, and inadequate antenatal care are prevalent. This study presents a comprehensive analysis of severe IDA during labour and its consequences on both maternal and neonatal outcomes.

Demographics and Risk Factors

The predominance of young women (mean age 25.23 years) and majority belonging to lower socioeconomic status (65%) with large number of unbooked cases (62%) poor antenatal coverage underscores systemic gaps in maternal healthcare. Similar observations were made by Toteja *et al.*, who reported anaemia in over 70% of pregnant women in rural India.^[3] The strong association between lower education and reduced interpregnancy intervals highlights the cyclical nature of nutritional depletion in successive pregnancies.

The high prevalence of anaemia among multigravida women (87%) supports previous findings that repeated pregnancies without adequate recovery time lead to cumulative iron depletion.^[6]

Dietary data revealed 56% were vegetarians, which may

have contributed to poor iron intake, as vegetarian diets are often low in heme iron and may have reduced bioavailability due to phytates and tannins.^[10]

Clinical Presentation and Laboratory Findings

Generalized weakness, giddiness, and pedal oedema were the most common symptoms. However, many cases of chronic anaemia were asymptomatic until the increased physiological stress of labour. Laboratory studies confirmed that the majority (74%) exhibited microcytic hypochromic anaemia, the hallmark of iron deficiency.

Maternal Complications

A high proportion of women developed preterm labour (45%), which is consistent with the study by Kumar *et al.* who reported a correlation between third-trimester anaemia and increased risk of preterm birth and low birth weight.^[9] Other complications such as postpartum haemorrhage, gestational hypertension, sepsis, and even maternal death were also observed, reaffirming anaemia's contribution to maternal morbidity and mortality.

Although severe anaemia alone may not directly cause death, it significantly reduces physiological reserve and tolerance to peripartum stress and bleeding.^[3] In this study, maternal death occurred in one woman with severe anaemia compounded by pre-eclampsia and sepsis.

Neonatal Outcomes

Neonatal outcomes were notably poor. 63% of infants were born with low birth weight, and 13% were stillbirths. These findings are in line with global evidence that maternal iron deficiency affects placental and fetal development, resulting in intrauterine growth restriction (IUGR), stillbirth, and neonatal death.^[8]

NICU admissions (27%) further reflect the burden of neonatal complications, often requiring intensive monitoring and care. Evidence suggests that improving maternal haemoglobin during pregnancy can improve birth weight and neonatal vitality.^[7]

Treatment and Delivery

Blood transfusion was necessary in 59% of cases,

emphasizing the emergency nature of these admissions. Injectable iron therapy (34%) was effective in some cases, especially when administered in the second or early third trimester. The majority of patients delivered vaginally, but emergency cesarean section was performed in 24%, often due to fetal distress or maternal decompensation.

The correlation of lower haemoglobin with higher parity, fewer ANC visits, and low educational status suggests a need for aggressive public health strategies focused on prevention.

CONCLUSION

Severe iron deficiency anaemia during labour is a significant risk factor for adverse maternal and neonatal outcomes. This study found a high incidence of preterm labour, postpartum haemorrhage, NICU admissions, low birth weight, and stillbirths among anaemic mothers. The findings emphasize the urgent need for early identification and management of anaemia during pregnancy, particularly in underserved populations.

Contributing factors such as low socioeconomic status, poor dietary habits, multiparity, and inadequate antenatal care were strongly associated with anaemia. Public health strategies must target these determinants through:

- Strengthened antenatal surveillance with routine haemoglobin estimation
- Early iron supplementation and nutritional counselling
- Family planning and inter pregnancy spacing
- Education and empowerment of women to improve healthcare utilisation

In the labour setting, the availability of parenteral iron, blood transfusion services, and close monitoring is crucial to reduce complications. Delivery of severely anaemic women should ideally occur in a tertiary care centre with ICU and blood bank support. Ultimately, multidisciplinary efforts are required to reduce the burden of maternal anaemia and improve maternal and neonatal outcomes in resource-constrained settings.

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(Vancouver Style)

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